

Chemical durability of glass fibres insulation used in nuclear power plants.

J. Micháľková^{*1}, J. Vokelová¹, B. Hruska² M. Chromčíková^{3,4}, M. Liška^{3,4}

¹ FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2,
SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

(E-mail: jaroslava.michalkova@tnuni.sk)

² Central Laboratories, FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2,
911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

³ VILA – Joined Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, FChPT STU, Študentská 2,
SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

⁴ VILA, FunGlass, A. Dubcek University of Trenčín, Študentská 2,
SK-911 50 Trenčín, Slovakia

ABSTRACT

In the case of the loss of coolant accident (LOCA) the glass fibres used as thermal and electrical insulation in PWR type nuclear power plant get in immediate contact with cooling solution of the emergency cooling system. Corrosion products formed during the contact insulation fibres with aggressive cooling solution can cause changes, resulting in insufficient even functionless operation of the cooling system. To assure safety of the cooling system it is important to know and describe behavior of insulating fibres in aggressive environment. Therefore the present work concerns chemical durability of the NUKON glass fibres used as insulating materials in nuclear power plants. Describes the static and dynamic tests, kinetics of transfer of the glass into the solution Tests were conducted in two corrosive medias - distilled water and corrosion solution $H_3BO_3/Na_2B_4O_7$ at temperatures 70 °C, 80 °C and 90 °C. Content of the elements was determined by atomic emission spectrometry with inductively coupled plasma VARIAN - Vista MPX/ICP-OES. Changes on the surface of the tested samples were observed by using scanning electron microscopy with energio-dispersion spectroscopy. Time dependences of normalized quantities of individual elements were described by regression function designed by Helebrant's model. From the results of static and dynamic tests follows that normalized elements in distilled water at different temperatures have different course than in the corrosive solution $H_3BO_3/Na_2B_4O_7$ and with increasing temperature tends to increase the normalized quantity of leaching elements in various corrosive solutions. The values of normalized quantities of elements set out in both corrosive solutions provided comparable results with values translated by empirical equation.

Keywords: Glass fibres, thermal insulation, LOCA, coolant solution, chemical durability, corrosion.

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